

Research

TVET for Socio-Economic Development in Malawi: Gaining Insights from China's Vocational Education System

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Abstract

Numerous studies have demonstrated the significant influence that Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) has on a nation's economic growth, as evidenced by the success story of countries like China. This study examined the current state of the Malawi TVET system, its challenges, and its potential to contribute to socioeconomic growth, employing qualitative methods and document analysis. The documents analysed were journal articles focusing on Malawi's and Chinese TVET systems, government reports, TVET policies, and documents from UNESCO, OECD, the International Labour Organisation and the World Bank. Results revealed crucial challenges, including inadequate infrastructure, a lack of financial resources, the absence of research centres and a mismatch between industry's needs and the training delivered at vocational institutions. Insights from China's successful TVET experience, which led to higher enrolment and employment rates through consistent funding, focused policies, private sector involvement, and offering incentives to entice students towards TVET, were analysed.

The study concludes by drawing lessons that Malawi can adopt from the Chinese TVET system, such as developing a consistent funding system, improving collaboration between different government ministries and departments, adopting Confucianism education philosophy, establishing research centres specifically focused on TVET, enhancing TVET institution-enterprise collaboration, and developing a comprehensive TVET teacher training programme.

Keywords: Technical Vocational Education and Training (TVET); Socio-Economic Development; Malawi; China

Introduction

Enhancing vocational education is a crucial strategic imperative for countries worldwide, as it directly aligns with the demands of the modern workforce. Due to its close links to real-world professions, vocational education plays a key role in addressing a variety of contemporary societal challenges. It contributes to the socio-economic development of the world (1). Multinational donor organisations have emphasised the growing significance of Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) for national development, pointing out that TVET gives people the skills and knowledge they need to enter the workforce and support their local economies (2–4). For instance, the Chinese government has placed a high value on vocational education, highlighting its contribution to both educational innovation and socioeconomic development (5). Similarly, to construct and upgrade their facilities and generate more related jobs nationwide, the U.K. government spent £400 million to support 62 continuing education institutions (6). Furthermore, the Southern African Development Community (SADC) member states have created and implemented legislation and policies to enhance the functionality of TVET systems during the last 20 years. Among the reforms are the creation of

Quality Assurance Bodies and frameworks, and National Qualification Authorities and National Qualification Frameworks (7).

Without exception, TVET in Malawi has its roots in providing skilled labour to support the nation's economic development and reduce poverty. In Malawi, vocational training was introduced in the colonial era (1891-1964), when it was mostly informal and focused on agricultural skills and basic trades (8). After attaining independence in 1964, the government established formal technical and vocational institutions, which mainly emphasised the agriculture and manufacturing sectors. In 1999, the government of Malawi established the Technical, Entrepreneurial and Vocational Education and Training Authority (TEVETA), aimed at enhancing the accessibility, quality, and relevance of vocational education and training (9).

Vocational training in Malawi is provided through Skills Development Centers (CSDCs), Community Technical Colleges (CTCs), National Technical Colleges (NTCs), and commercial institutions. The training is divided into three categories: formal, informal, and nonformal. It is integrated into the general educational system; after completing two years of junior secondary school, students can choose to pursue vocational education (10). The Ministry of Education, Science, and Technology (MOEST) and the Ministry of Labour now oversee vocational education, with the Ministry of Economic Planning and Development and the Ministry of Industry and Trade also playing a role. Vocational institutions have different governance systems; the Malawi government directly governs some, while others have intricate agreements with local boards or religious entities.

Funding for vocational training is provided by student fees, government funding, and a 1% levy on employers' gross wages that the Malawi Revenue Authority oversees. The MRA reimburses companies for their training expenses (11).

The importance of TVET in combating the demands for skilled manpower essential for sectors like agriculture, construction, manufacturing, commerce and transportation has been recognised in most parts of the world (2). This includes Malawi, which is pivotal to national development. By nurturing the knowledge and skills necessary for these fields, TVET serves as a key pathway toward the provision of a capable workforce. Previous studies support TVET as a worthwhile investment for both developing and developed countries, where it enhances economic resilience and meets the ever-changing industry demands.

According to Mutebi (12) TVET has been strengthened as a key platform for imparting the practical knowledge and competencies needed for the workforce in response to global challenges such as poverty, unemployment, and rapidly advancing technology. The main role of TVET is particularly to help youth and adults advance their skills, knowledge, values, and attitudes required by the industry, hence contributing to workplace effectiveness and national economic development (13). By equipping individuals, especially in rural and urban areas reliant on subsistence agriculture, with practical and marketable skills, vocational education can empower communities to diversify their source of income, enhance productivity and participate in higher-value economic activities. This is particularly important as Malawi seeks to expand sectors such as non-traditional agriculture, renewable energy and mining.

Integrating vocational education and training into the broader economic recovery strategies could bridge the skills gap in emerging industries while offering immediate pathways out of poverty for many Malawians. Malawi's Vision 2063 recognises TVET as key to achieving national goals, including social cohesion, technological advancement, economic diversification, poverty alleviation and industrialisation. It envisages transforming Malawi into a middle-income country by building a well-educated and skilled workforce which can adapt to the ever-changing industry, through improved partnerships with the industry, promoting entrepreneurship, and enhancing quality assurance and infrastructure development (14). This study explores the status of TVET in Malawi, the challenges hindering the effectiveness of the TVET system towards enhancing socioeconomic development, and recommendations for improvement, drawing lessons from China's TVET model.

Conceptual framework

By adapting China's successful model, the researcher proposes a three-pillar conceptual framework to improve Malawi's TVET system. The framework places a strong emphasis on (1) reforming governance and policy, such as interministerial coordination and fixed budget allocations; (2) improving industry-academia collaboration through enterprise partnerships and demand-driven "Key Schools"; and (3) increasing capacity through student incentives, infrastructure improvements, and instructor training. Together, these pillars can help address Malawi's key challenges of resource limitations, skill mismatches, and fragmented policies. Malawi may learn from China's TVET accomplishments, which are fueled by industrial integration, strategic funding, and high-quality investments. Malawi can turn vocational education into a catalyst for socioeconomic growth by institutionalising these strategies, which would enhance employment results and match training to market demands. The framework emphasises the significance of contextual factors while offering a roadmap for policy implementation.

Materials and Methods

This study used a qualitative method utilising document analysis to explore the status of TVET in Malawi and China and assess how TVET in Malawi can enhance socio-economic development. Published and unpublished sources, including reports, government publications, journal articles, theses and dissertations, conference proceedings, policies, and organisational websites for specific organisations such as OECD, ILO and UNESCO were analysed to gain a detailed and contextual understanding of Malawi's and China's TVET systems. An in-depth analysis focused on designing, implementing, and evaluating TVET programs and their links to socio-economic development. A detailed cross-checking and verification of data sources of literature was conducted to ensure fairness, accuracy, and insightfulness to meet the study objectives. In addition, strategies, reports, and policies focusing on TVET from recognised non-governmental organisations, public and private institutions, and government bodies were reviewed. This methodology provided comprehensive insights into the contextual and operational aspects of the Chinese TVET system and their relevance to Malawi's socio-economic development.

Results and Discussions

Malawi's socio-economic context

According to the Danish Trade Union Development Agency (15) Malawi's GDP growth was estimated at 1.5% in 2023, a modest increase from 0.9% in 2022, but still displaying a slowdown compared to the previous years. The poor development had been aggravated by natural catastrophes like Cyclone Freddy slowed down industrial activity by reducing agricultural output and taking out a third of the nation's electricity generation. Inflation increased from 20.8% in 2022 to 28% in 2023 (16). Despite undergoing economic growth, Malawi is still faced with abject poverty. Vocational education and training present a vital opportunity to address this challenge.

Employment status in Malawi

According to Baulch et al. (17) Employment in Malawi is largely centred on agriculture, with subsistence farming dominating the labour market. Unemployment is reported at a low 5% (18), mainly due to the prevalence of informal sector employment; however, underemployment and low-quality jobs, especially in rural areas, remain significant issues (15). These challenges emanate from economic weaknesses, including limited industrial development, a lack of employment diversification and skill mismatches. Enhancing the quality of TVET and expanding vocational training is critical towards addressing under-employment and low-quality jobs by equipping the youth and elderly with employable and entrepreneurial skills. Improving the quality of TVET and expanding vocational education and training is critical towards addressing under-employment and low-quality jobs by equipping the youth and elderly with employable and entrepreneurial skills.

Current status of TVET in Malawi

Successes in Malawi's TVET system

TVET in Malawi has registered some successes. According to the Malawi TEVET Authority (19), these successes include; giving the Malawi Institute of Education (MIE) more authority over curriculum development, establishing cooperations with organisations that support the development of small-scale businesses, a growing number of registered TVET providers, a notable expansion and restructuring of the formal and informal TVET market, providing education and training funding for TVET students, and introducing mobile training workshops to expand access to TVET. Furthermore, with improved access to TVET, the Danish Trade Union Development Agency (15) indicated a 37% increase in recruitments from 2013 to 2017 and an increased number of training providers, whilst Kajawo (20) stated an improvement in providing vocational training in Malawi's correctional centres (prisons) from 14% in 2018 to 23% in 2020. In addition, the sector has also established a quality assurance framework (7). Regardless of these successes, TVET in Malawi is still facing challenges as highlighted below.

Challenges hindering the effectiveness of the TVET system in Malawi

The quality of graduates from Malawi's TVET institutions is an increasing concern in the industry. The mismatch between TVET graduates' skills and the competencies needed to achieve their productivity needs is a common source of dissatisfaction among industries (21). Due to this gap, TVET graduates have higher rates of underemployment and unemployment.

These challenges are a sign of a larger problem: a drop in economic competitiveness and productivity, which makes it even harder for the labour market to absorb qualified workers successfully (22) as presented below;

Poor curriculum design and relevance

The findings show that the irrelevance of the curriculum is one of the critical challenges Malawi is facing (23). As technology in the industries progresses, coupled with the changing labour market demands, the curricula for many vocational training programs become outdated, which is enhanced by the poor participation of the industry in TVET (21). This is not in line with Osidipe (24) which states that TVET institutions need to collaborate with employers since they are the end users of their products to ensure that the graduates are fully prepared for the labour market. This obsolete curriculum does not prepare vocational graduates adequately for the world of work. The poor curriculum design and misalignment result in a significant skills mismatch, with graduates lacking the crucial knowledge and skills required by the labour market, thereby affecting productivity.

Inadequate resources and infrastructure

Inadequate financial resources limit the provision of recommended training materials and the enrollment of qualified staff (25). The shortage of training resources significantly undermines the effectiveness of TVET institutions in Malawi. Many centres lack qualified instructors, adequate facilities, modern equipment, and instructional materials essential for practical, hands-on training (26). Moreover, poor coordination among key financiers of the TVET system in Malawi, including the government, employers, non-governmental organisations, donors and households, resulted in duplicated efforts (27).

Limited technological advancement and innovation

A significant barrier to the growth and relevance of TVET in Malawi is the lack of innovation within the sector. Innovation in TVET is essential for making vocational training more responsive to the needs of the industry (28). There is a growing consensus in the literature on innovation studies that any functional innovation system must include the TVET sector (29–31). Unfortunately, in Malawi, many institutions operate without intellectual property protection or access to technology transfer resources, which stifles creativity, innovation, and entrepreneurial initiatives among graduates (32). Without these systems, TVET institutions struggle to produce innovative solutions that align with industry demands or contribute to economic growth.

Lack of focused Research and informed policy development

The lack of dedicated research institutions for TVET in Malawi is a barrier to socioeconomic development (33) agreeing with Raman et al. (34) who stated that conducting research is critical because it creates knowledge to guide curriculum design and policy development, assesses program development and encourages innovation to guarantee alignment with the needs of the labour market. To add on that, Mulder (35) indicates that research in TVET is a catalyst for social justice and economic growth, especially for marginalised groups. The mismatch between TVET graduates' skills and the demands of the industry is perpetuated by the lack of research focused on TVET. There is limited capacity to conduct in-depth analysis of challenges hindering the effectiveness of the sector, hence decisions are made without sufficient data to inform program design, curriculum development and resource allocation.

Shortage of employment opportunities

According to Yu et al. (36) "One person in vocational education means one person employed and one household lifted out of poverty." Despite this expectation, vocational training in Malawi has failed to usher all graduates into the world of work. The study reveals that the TEVET Authority (37) indicates that about 35% of TVET graduates remain unemployed 2 years after completing vocational training, undermining the intended socioeconomic impact of TVET and disagreeing with Yu et al. (5) and the OECD (38). This highlights that vocational training is meant to elevate a country's social and economic development by enhancing employment, which is not true for Malawi. As indicated by UNESCO (23) Contributing factors include limited access to job placement services, industry attachments, and the exclusion of marginalised groups such as individuals with disabilities, the elderly, and disadvantaged communities.

The status of China's TVET system and its impact on economic development

Brief history of China's TVET system

China's steadfast investment in TVET has made it a global model for vocational education. According to Chen et al. (39), starting in 1963, the World Bank heavily funded TVET in developing countries, with lending peaking at 51% of total education expenses by 1976. By the year 2002, funding towards TVET had dropped to 9% as the World Bank and other donors shifted focus to other priority areas, which were considered more profitable (40). Unlike other developing countries, China prioritised vocational education while many African countries, including Malawi, reduced funding

following international advice, hindering socioeconomic development. China's continued investment in TVET has enhanced the sector's development, offering valuable lessons for Malawi. A few decades ago, both nations shared similar histories of poverty alleviation and education challenges, but China's consistent investment in vocational education improved its socioeconomic development, making it a relevant model for Malawi to emulate.

The status of TVET in China

China's educational system includes primary, secondary, higher education and vocational training. TVET, often referred to as Zhíyè jiàoyù (职业教育) in China, is essential for fulfilling the needs of the country's quickly developing economy (41)

The structure of TVET in China

According to Chen et al. (39) China's TVET system is designed to support social and economic development through a multi-level structure covering secondary, post-secondary, and continuing education. Secondary vocational education targets students after nine years of compulsory schooling, combining general and vocational training. Post-secondary vocational education provides advanced skills through diplomas and bachelor's programs, preparing students for technical and managerial roles (5). Continuing vocational education offers professional skill enhancement through Adult Education Centers and enterprise-based training tailored to industry needs. TVET in China caters for diverse age groups and career stages (42).

Enrollment status of vocational training in China

Yu et al. (36) indicate that China's TVET system has demonstrated significant growth and impact, with over 4,500 higher vocational education and secondary schools supporting technical education in close to 110,000 primary and middle schools, benefiting over 15 million students annually. The Ministry of Education states that in the year 2022, China had 7,201 secondary vocational institutions, and 33% of upper secondary school general enrolment was in vocational training. Similarly, the higher vocational training level, with 1,521 schools, claimed 46.29% of the total undergraduate enrolment. The increase in enrollment was due to the policies developed by the Chinese government focused on enhancing TVET institutions and industry collaborations, fostering increased access and inclusivity, and quality improvement. These policies promoted vocational education as an alternative to academic pathways (43).

Strategies China incorporated to boost the TVET system

The primary goal for TVET in China is to increase quality. Reforms that include new technologies like artificial intelligence (AI), robotics and big data in the curriculum make education more relevant to the workforce (44). For quality TVET to be achieved, China has put in place many strategies to ensure that the skills training institutions impart to the students meet the needs of the industry and eventually enhance its economic development. The strategies have been highlighted below;

Reforming governance and policy

The government's commitment towards TVET

According to Mehrotra & Gandhi (45) the Chinese government allocated 20% of the annual education budget to TVET by the 1996 law of vocational education. This constant funding, in addition to local revenue initiatives and the 1.5% of industries' payroll that goes towards vocational training, shows the commitment of the government towards investing in vocational education. Furthermore, Policies such as the "Outline of the National Plan for Medium and Long-Term Education Reform and Development (2010–2020)" and the "Modern Vocational Education System Construction Plan (2014–2020)" emphasise integrating vocational education at all levels, establishing applied science universities, and fostering lifelong learning (46). These efforts have improved the effectiveness of TVET in China through the support of career clusters, modern apprenticeships, and training in advanced manufacturing and green technology, aligning with strategies like *Made in China 2025* and *Digital China Construction*. The modernised system, set for full implementation by 2025, aims to close the skills gap and produce a labour force skilled enough to drive sustainable and innovation-based economic growth.

Developing comprehensive policies focused on TVET.

Table 1: Sample of Vocational Education Policies

Policy	Issuing department
Implementation Plan for Empowering Industry – Education Integration in Vocational Education (2023-2025)	Ministry of Education, State-owned Assets Supervision and Administration, Ministry of Finance, Ministry of Natural Resources, People's Bank of China, Ministry of Industry and Information Technology, National Development and Reform Commission, Commission of the State Council, and Ministry of Human Resources and Social Security.
Action Plan for Improving the Quality of Vocational Education (2020-2023)	National Development and Reform Commission, State Council Leading Group Office of Poverty Alleviation and Development of China, State Taxation Administration, Ministry of Education, Ministry of Industry and Information Technology, Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Affairs, Ministry of Finance, Ministry of Human Resources, and Ministry of Social Security, State-owned Assets Supervision and Administration Commission of the State Council.

Source: Yu et al. (2025)

China's transition to high-quality socio-economic growth and industry modernisation highlights the need for skilled technical professionals. From China's TVET policies, it has been highlighted that the Vocational Training Law redefines TVET as an equal counterpart to general education, focusing on enhancing employability, technical skills, and professional ethics (36). The development of the TVET policies in Table 1 indicates collaboration among several stakeholders in vocational training implementation, government coordination, school-enterprise collaboration, social engagement and industry guidance is promoted through these laws. Major reforms highlighted through the policies include the recognition of TVET qualifications via a credit bank, integration of general and vocational education systems and enhancing industry support (36).

Utilising Confucianism in Vocational Training

According to Wang (47) Confucianism is the fundamental moral and philosophical concept in Chinese societies, founded by the Chinese politician, philosopher, and educator Confucius (551–479 BC) 2500 years ago. It addresses social, ethical, educational, economic and governmental facets of all societal levels. Chinese higher vocational education and training are influenced by Confucianism in several areas, such as curriculum design, learning objectives, student mobility, and graduate employment (48). For instance, Feng and Newton in the year 2012 taught a Master's course on sustainability education that was founded on the Confucian harmony principle. The findings demonstrated that by addressing sustainability issues about people and their varied interests, the Confucian principle of harmony can support the implementation of sustainability education. It can support group efforts and cooperation (47).

Collaboration between different government ministries and departments

The "Action Plan for Improving the Quality of Vocational Education (2020-2023)" demonstrates collaborative efforts among different stakeholders such as the Ministry of Human Resources and Social Security, Ministry of Finance, Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Affairs, State Taxation Administration, and State-owned Assets Supervision and Administration Commission of the State Council, are essential for shaping effective TVET policies in China (36). These cooperations ensure social equity policies, industry alignment and quality, fostering innovation and inclusivity while advancing high-quality vocational education and training development.

Enhance TVET institution-enterprise collaboration.

Establishment of vocational education administration groups

China has established vocational administration groups focusing on the administration, development, implementation and promotion of vocational education programs (39). By 2014, China had over 1000 vocational education groups which managed to unite schools, enterprises, industry associations, and government agencies and improve facilities, teacher qualifications, and urban-rural development while addressing labour market needs (1). The groups have enhanced the alignment of curricula and industry needs, improving the quality of TVET.

Capacity and quality enhancement

Offering students incentives to participate in TVET

Wang & Tian (49) indicates that negative perception towards TVET has been a challenge in China. To curb this challenge, the Chinese government introduced financial subsidies and free secondary vocational education, targeting the marginalised and underprivileged in rural areas. The subsidies helped increase access to vocational education and improve retention and completion rates by alleviating financial stress and enhancing lifelong learning and skills development, which are crucial in the rapidly changing industry. By 2015, 91% of vocational students accessed free education, with 40% qualifying for national subsidies (39). This initiative has elevated the social status of the youth and the elderly, especially in rural areas, eventually contributing significantly to the employment of the youth and labour market outcomes. By 2016, the employment rate of high vocational graduates was 91.5% (50)

Comprehensive TVET teacher education

According to Fan et al. (51) China's strategies for TVET teacher development focus on building "dual-qualified" teacher teams "Dual-qualified" vocational teacher is defined as an instructor who has both teaching and specific vocational field qualifications. The benefit of the dual qualification is that it allows educators to bridge the gap between theory and practical application. Key frameworks that enhanced the "dual qualified" teacher include the 2019 "National Vocational Education Reform Implementation Plan" and the 2022 "Opinions on Deepening the Reform of Modern Vocational Education System Construction," which emphasise enhancing teacher qualifications, professional development, and industry integration. Through partnerships with enterprises, professional training, and incentives for industry involvement, teachers gain practical expertise and align curricula with market demands. Osidiye (52) indicates that by 2019 China had 160 higher education institutions and more than 250 specialised teacher training bases established since 1989 to ensure a steady supply of well-qualified vocational teachers significantly improving the quality of training and leading to a noteworthy workforce shift for instance, from 1990 to 2015, employment in agriculture fell from 60.1% to 28.3%, while manufacturing rose to 29.3% and services to 42.4% (53). Reflecting the impact of a growing skilled labour force on industrial and service sector growth.

Focused research on vocational education

Zhang et al. (54) highlight the New Era China Vocational Education Research Center at Shenzhen Polytechnic University as an example of China's commitment towards advancing vocational training by driving innovation, aligning training with industry demands and promoting evidence-based practices. The research centre focuses on innovation, a digital economy-focused curriculum, and school-enterprise collaboration. Shenzhen Research Centre comprises 16 full-time researchers, including overseas-trained experts, professors and part-time scholars. Research centres are important in enhancing the relevance and quality of TVET. Due to the availability of such research centres, China's level of innovation has increased substantially throughout the years, as indicated by the National Bureau of Statistics (55), which highlighted the growth of China's Innovation Index and its sub-indices (Innovation Environment, Input, Output, and Effectiveness), the consistent rise from 2015 to 2023 across all indices reflected significant advancements in China's innovation ecosystem. China's TVET system significantly boosts innovation by producing a skilled workforce, fostering entrepreneurship, and enabling technology transfer.

Developing a resource database for vocational education

Yu et al. (56) indicate that China has developed a national teaching resource database to support vocational teachers, facilitate self-regulated learning and enhance the quality of vocational education through centralised access to high-quality instructional materials such as lesson plans, assessment tools and multi-media content. This is aligned with UNESCO's Beijing Consensus on Artificial Intelligence and Education 2019 (57) and OECD's Digital Strategies in Education (58). The government of China emphasises informatisation in TVET to create a "smart Education of China" with high-quality resource sharing and service. By 2023, 2,154 schools and 2,838 enterprises had been involved in establishing 203 national and 582 provincial teaching resource databases (56).

Recommendations

Many studies have demonstrated the critical role of TVET in economic development. Vocational education has been recognised as a valuable component of economic growth in many developed countries, including China. With the development of TVET, China has gained many successes in the science and technology field, which has considerably

increased the well-being of Chinese people. China's steady and consistent growth as a global power has been linked to the exceptional provision of school-based TVET (45,52,59).

Though many studies and practical experiences in many countries have experienced challenges in learning from other countries, gaining insights from a successful system to improve skills attainment, innovation and creativity, based on local contexts, could be a practical solution to combat TVET challenges in Malawi.

Reforming governance and policy

Effective TVET funding

As indicated by the findings, Malawi can draw lessons from China's funding practices by dedicating a fixed budget percentage to TVET, which is in line with Mehrotra et al. (45) who highlighted that empowering local governments to implement flexible programs and mandating industry contributions for workforce training. In addition, agreeing with Feng et al. (60) Adopting "Key schools" could also help strategically address critical skill gaps, improve employment outcomes, and drive economic growth in Malawi.

Improve collaboration between different ministries and departments.

Malawi can draw valuable lessons from China's collaborative approach to TVET governance, as indicated by Yu et al. (36), where multiple government ministries and departments such as Ministries of Labour, Trade, Education, Finance and Economic Affairs, Health, Information and Digitalization, Agriculture, Youth & Sports, and Ministry of Local Government, Unity & Culture work together to develop and implement effective policies and ensure that TVET programs align with societal, economic, industrial, and labour market needs. Agreeing with the British Council and Da (61,62) TVET collaboration between various government bodies on TVET issues puts vocational education on the right track. The joint efforts can improve the relevance and quality of TVET, fostering creativity, innovation and inclusivity.

Adopt Confucianism as an educational philosophy.

By implementing a curriculum inspired by Confucian principles, Malawi can structure its TVET programs to prioritise societal problem-solving, ethical work practices, and community-centred development. For instance, as highlighted by Wang (47) Integrating a "needs of society" curriculum could align vocational training with local economic demands, such as agriculture, renewable energy, and small-scale manufacturing, addressing skill gaps in these critical sectors. Moreover, the Confucian model's focus on discipline, respect for learning, and lifelong education aligns well with the need to instill a culture of professionalism and adaptability in Malawi's workforce (63).

Enhance TVET institution-enterprise collaboration.

Malawi needs to ensure that Industries actively participate in skills training from curriculum development to graduate welfare (64). According to insights from Chen et al. (39) the Malawi government should put in place influential measures to motivate employers to participate in vocational training actively, such as tax reduction, recognition and certification programs for the most active industries. Malawi can adopt any of the following models of TVET industry collaboration, defined by Joo (2013) as cited in Osidipe (65) the "Mutual Cooperation Between Enterprise and TVET Institution" model emphasises shared benefits: enterprises improve production and productivity, while TVET institutions access equipment, expertise, and financial support. Second, the "Training by Order" model focuses on a specific enterprise that partners with the institution to offer specialised programs and restructure teaching to meet the enterprise's needs, with enterprises providing funding, equipment, and instructors. To add on that, the "Zero Period of Adaptation" model aims to directly prepare trainees for employment by customizing courses based on industry requirements and providing field practice. Finally, the "Combined School-Factory" model involves establishing joint school-factory enterprises that cater to local economic needs, allowing teachers to gain real-world experience while improving curriculum content.

Capacity and quality enhancement

Establish research centres specifically for TVET.

Establishing dedicated research centres in Malawi's vocational training institutions could foster creativity and innovation, provide evidence-based insights for policy development, and align training programs with the requirements of the industry (33). Learning from Zhang et al. (54) The research centres could focus on theoretical advancements in vocational education, technological advancements, special needs of particular communities, tracking school-enterprise

partnerships, and reforming curricula to address emerging trends. By using research to shape policies and enhance institutional practices, Malawi could enhance the relevance and quality of TVET programs, ensuring they produce a workforce fully equipped to meet the demands of the evolving labour market and contribute to the socio-economic development of the country.

Develop a comprehensive TVET teacher training programme.

The ability of TVET systems to deliver relevant and high-quality training is mostly dependent on the quality of their trainers and instructors, and consequently, on the calibre of their teacher training programs (66). Malawi can draw valuable lessons from China's robust TVET teacher training framework and strategies for teacher development through building "dual-qualified" teacher teams, blending theoretical instruction with practical application to meet industry needs, as highlighted by Fan et al. (51). Malawi may also develop policies prioritising teacher qualification enhancement, continuous professional development, and strong industry integration, as recommended by Yu et al. (5). This can be achieved by developing a strong teacher training system in collaboration with higher education institutions and establishing specialised instructor training bases to ensure a steady supply of highly skilled TVET educators.

Conclusion

This study explored the status of the TVET system in Malawi and how the TVET system could be improved to boost socio-economic growth, as well as highlighting the critical role of vocational education in addressing the skills gap and aligning education with labour market demands. This eventually enhances employability and fosters entrepreneurship by equipping the youth and elderly with practical, job-ready skills. The results show that while Malawi's TVET system has the potential to contribute to poverty reduction and economic growth, it faces various challenges, including a lack of focused research centres, a shortage of infrastructure, irrelevance of the curriculum, a poor TVET teacher training system, and a lack of innovation in the sector. By drawing lessons from China's successful vocational education system, this study offered actionable measures for strengthening Malawi's TVET system. This includes providing consistent funding towards TVET, enhancing the TVET teacher training program, adopting Confucianism philosophy, improving innovation, establishing collaboration between different stakeholders and establishing research centres focused on TVET. In conclusion, the findings highlight the relevance of a well-functioning TVET system as a driver of socioeconomic development. Malawi can transform its TVET system into an effective tool for skills development, job creation, and economic growth by addressing identified challenges and leveraging China's best practices.

Limitations of the study

Since this study used a qualitative method, document analysis, it was difficult to measure how directly TVET affects Malawi's economic growth, labour market efficiency and employment rates. The statistical validation of TVET's contribution to economic growth is limited by the lack of empirical data. For a more thorough grasp of TVET's efficacy, future studies should use quantitative approaches to offer data-driven insights and comparison evaluations with other developing economies.

Second, this study focuses mostly on highlighting the significance of industry-TVET collaboration and does not offer a thorough assessment of successful models of partnerships. Furthermore, there is insufficient empirical data to measure the direct impact of these partnerships on vocational graduates' skill alignment with the labour market demands and employability. Future studies should investigate certain frameworks and conduct quantitative analyses to see how well industry-TVET collaborations handle skills mismatches.

Implications for future research

Future studies should focus on quantitative methods to assess the direct impact of TVET on Malawi's labour market efficiency, economic growth and employment rates. Empirical research could offer statistical evidence of TVET's contribution towards national development, enabling policy-makers to make evidence-based decisions.

In addition, future research should examine effective approaches for enhancing industry-TVET partnerships by identifying feasible models for establishing collaborations between TVET institutions and the labour market. Strengthening these partnerships will guarantee that TVET programs meet the labour market needs, enhancing the employability of graduates and resolving skill gaps.

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